

REPORT

The XXXIV International Conference on Multivariate Statistical Analysis, 16–18 November 2015, Łódź, Poland

The 34th edition of the International Conference on **Multivariate Statistical Analysis** was held in **Łódź, Poland** on November 16-18, 2015. The MSA 2015 conference was organized by the **Department of Statistical Methods** of the University of Lodz, the **Institute of Statistics and Demography** of the University of Lodz, the **Polish Statistical Association** and the **Committee on Statistics and Econometrics of Polish Academy of Sciences**. The Organizing Committee was headed by **Professor Czesław Domański**. The scientific secretaries included Anna Jurek, M.Sc. and Elżbieta Zalewska, M.Sc. from the Department of Statistical Methods of the University of Lodz.

The Mayor of the City of Łódź, Hanna Zdanowska took the honorary patronage of the Multivariate Statistical Analysis MSA 2015 conference. Its organization was financially supported by the **National Bank of Poland**, the **Polish Academy of Sciences**, the **Łódź City Council** and **StatSoft Polska Sp. z o.o.**

The 2015 edition, as all previous Multivariate Statistical Analysis conferences, aimed at creating the opportunity for scientists and practitioners of statistics to present and discuss the latest theoretical achievements in the field of the multivariate statistical analysis, its practical aspects and applications. A number of the presented and discussed statistical issues were based on questions identified during previous MSA conferences. The scientific programme covered various statistical problems, including multivariate estimation methods, statistical tests, non-parametric inference, discrimination analysis, Monte Carlo analysis, Bayesian inference, application of statistical methods in finance and economy, especially methods used in capital market and risk management. The range of topics also included the design of experiments and survey sampling methodology, mainly for the social science purposes. The conference was attended by 93 participants from main academic centres in Poland (Białystok, Katowice, Kraków, Olsztyn, Opole, Poznań, Rzeszów, Szczecin, Toruń, Warszawa and Wrocław) and from abroad (Lithuania). The list of participants included scientists, academic tutors as well as representatives of the National Bank of Poland, local statistical offices and business. In 17 sessions 59 papers were presented, including 2 invited lectures.

The conference was opened by the Head of the Organizing Committee, **Professor Czesław Domański**. The subsequent speakers at the conference opening were **Professor Włodzimierz Nykiel**, the Rector of the University of Lodz and **Professor Pawel Starosta**, the Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Sociology of the University of Lodz.

After the opening ceremony, all participants had the opportunity to attend the invited lecture by **Professor Włodzimierz Okrasa** (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw) *Statistical Process as a Social Process of Quantification*. The second invited lecture was presented by **Professor Krzysztof Najman**, **Professor Kamila Migdal-Najman** and **Professor Mirosław Szreder** (University of Gdańsk), and was dedicated to *Big Data - new opportunities, new restrictions*. At the conference closing the participants attended the lecture by **Professor Czesław Domański** (University of Lodz) entitled *Meaning of models and statistics in the process of statistical inference*.

Among regular conference sessions, the historical plenary session was held, chaired by **Professor Janusz Wywiał**, dedicated to eminent Polish scientists. **Professor Tadeusz Gerstenkorn** (University of Lodz) recalled his memories of Włodzimierz Kryszicki. **Professors Tadeusz Kowaleski** (University of Lodz) presented statistical threads in the work of Jan Długosz. **Professor Jan Kordos** (Warsaw Management University) presented his cooperation with Professor Tadeusz Walczak. **Professor Czesław Domański** (University of Lodz) presented Stanisław Staszic as a sympathizer of Łódź.

Other sessions were chaired respectively by:

SESSION II	Professor Włodzimierz Okrasa (Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw)
SESSION III	Professor Andrzej Sokołowski (Cracow University of Economics)
SESSION IV A	Professor Tomasz Michalski (Warsaw School of Economics)
SESSION IV B	Professor Jerzy Korzeniewski (University of Lodz)
SESSION V	Professor Mirosław Krzyśko (Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań)
SESSION VI A	Professor Adam Śliwiński (Warsaw School of Economics)
SESSION VI B	Professor Katarzyna Stapor (The Silesian Technical University)
SESSION VII A	Professor Grażyna Trzpiot (University of Economics in Katowice)
SESSION VII B	Professor Marek Walesiak (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION VIII A	Professor Grzegorz Kończak (University of Economics in Katowice)

SESSION VIII B	Professor Elżbieta Gołata (Poznań University of Economics)
SESSION IX A	Professor Wojciech Zieliński (Warsaw University of Life Sciences)
SESSION IX B	Professor Małgorzata Markowska (Wrocław University of Economics)
SESSION X A	Professor Janusz Korol (Szczecin University)
SESSION X B	Professor Bronisław Ceranka (Poznań University of Life Sciences)
SESSION XI	Professor Józef Dziechciarz (Wrocław University of Economics)

The MSA 2015 conference was closed by the Chairman of the Organizing Committee, **Professor Czesław Domański**, who summarized the Conference as very effective and added that all discussions and doubts should become inspirations and strong motivations for further work for both scientists and practitioners. Finally, he thanked all the guests, conference partners and sponsors.

The next edition of Multivariate Statistical Analysis Conference **MSA 2016** is planned on **November 7-9, 2016** and will be held in **Łódź, Poland**. The Chairman of the Organizing Committee, **Professor Czesław Domański** informed that this will be the 35th edition of the conference and kindly invited all interested scientists, researchers and students to participate.

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